

MEC-based architecture for interoperable and trustworthy internet of moving things

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ABSTRACT

The expansion of the Internet of Moving Things (IoMT) leads to limitless and continuous working playgrounds exploited by highly dynamic end devices. This requires the adoption of multi-Radio Access Technologies (RATs)-based strategies to provide IoMT units with ubiquitous connectivity. To this end, the development of secure bootstrapping and authentication mechanisms is necessary to permit the secure operation of end devices. Given the transmission and power limitations of these elements, current cryptographic solutions do not address these stringent requirements. For that reason, in the study we present a Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC)-based end-to-end architecture that enables an efficient and secure authentication and key agreement between end devices and network servers over heterogeneous resource-limited networks such as the Low Power Wide Area Networks (LPWANs). Our proposal is based on the Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting (AAA) architecture and the recent Internet Engineering Task Force initiatives Static Context Header Compression and Low-Overhead CoAP-EAP. The results obtained from experimental tests reveal the validity of the proposal as it enables constrained IoMT devices to gain IPv6 connectivity as well as performs end-to-end secure authentication with notable reliability and controlled latency.

1. Introduction

The Internet of Moving Things (IoMT) proposes a constant and seamless connectivity of non-static devices. To make it happen, the recent rise of Low Power Wide Area Networks (LPWANs)-based solutions has enabled long-range communications with very low energy consumption for end devices. This fuels the development of ubiquitous IoMT systems that are able to provide services, regardless of the location or mobility conditions, e.g., goods tracking, vehicle monitoring, or eHealth applications [1].

However, the variety of available LPWAN-based Radio Access Technologies (RATs), e.g., LoRaWAN, Sigfox, and Narrow-Band IoT (NB-IoT), yields important challenges considering devices' interoperability and security because different network infrastructures that support end device's connectivity may present highly different characteristics. Regarding interoperability aspects, a common addressing, naming, and discovery scheme that could abstract the huge heterogeneity of IoMT units' hardware, software, and communication procedures is required. In

previous work, authors proposed the use of IPv6 as a common ground for enabling interoperability among different connected moving devices [2]. All-IP scenarios bring clear advantages for high-level protocol and application developers as the integration of IoMT devices within the Internet is straightforward. Regarding security, each communication infrastructure, like those mentioned above, presents its particular bootstrapping procedures for granting network access to end devices in a secure way. This functionality is a clear barrier in heterogeneous multi-LPWAN scenarios, where different Radio Access Networks (RANs) are available for relevant use-case in the IoMT. For that reason, a common authentication infrastructure is highly desirable instead of relying on the individual and non-compatible bootstrapping procedures of different communication architectures. This paves the way for the future integration of LPWANs within the 5G ecosystem [3]. Thus, the adoption of Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting (AAA) infrastructures is envisioned as a promising solution for the development of secure and RAN-independent IoMT systems [4]. Additionally, LPWAN security mechanisms are based on previous trust relationship or preprovided

cryptographic material, known as *managed* strategies [5,6]. This makes the IoMT a perfect candidate for benefiting from the AAA standardized framework as a method to offer scalability and improved security management. In this line, different frameworks have been proposed for state-of-the-art LPWANs such as Narrow Band-IoT(NB-IoT) [7] or Long Range Wide Area Network(LoRaWAN) [8], which currently are the most adopted solutions for providing long-range and efficient connectivity to IoT end devices [9].

When considering the interoperability and security solutions described above, i.e., the use of IPv6 in conjunction with the integration of the AAA-based cryptographic mechanisms, there is still an important challenge related to the replacement with a robust size of the messages exchanged by these authentication schemes when considering the severe restrictions of LPWANs. To avoid this issue, the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) has released the Static Context Header Compression (SCHC) scheme [10] that aims to permit the compression and fragmentation of long messages, e.g., IPv6 packets, to make them suitable to be transmitted over radio links with limited bandwidth resources. The functionality of this novel compression and fragmentation mechanism has been recently evaluated [7], showing promising results for transporting heavy application-level data over LoRaWAN links. Furthermore, given the aforementioned heterogeneity of IoMT end devices and transmission technologies, a supplementary layer within the communication architecture is desirable to provide an additional abstraction level. At this point, the Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) paradigm comes into play to host the required interoperability functions as well as other services to enrich the IoMT systems [11,12]. As discussed in [13,14], MEC-based architectures enhance the performance of IoMT deployments as they complement the limited computation and storage resources offered by end devices.

In this study, we propose to exploit and extend the full potential of the SCHC scheme embedded in an MEC-based architecture to compress the authentication messages generated by the novel Low-Overhead CoAP-EAP protocol (LO-CoAP-EAP) [8] mechanism. This approach permits an efficient and secure authentication and key agreement between end devices and network servers over constrained networks such as LPWANs. The main contributions of this study are the following: (i) an MEC-based solution for integrating advanced compression and fragmentation mechanisms in IoMT deployments; (ii) a functional AAA architecture for the secure bootstrapping of IoMT end devices, regardless of the underlying communication technology employed; (iii) a real-world implementation and experimental validation of the proposed system.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides the background regarding the employed interoperability, compression, fragmentation, and bootstrapping technologies. Section 3 introduces the MEC-based architecture and contextualizes our research proposal. Section 4 presents the implementation details. The validation results are shown and discussed in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 presents the conclusions and defines future ways.

2. Background

2.1. Interoperability based on IPv6, UDP, and COAP stack

To enable the interoperability between heterogeneous RATs, the IETF has worked on the standardization of a common Internet stack based on IPv6 and high-layer protocols such as User Datagram Protocol (UDP) and Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP) [15]. In the IoMT, this common stack provides great advantages for improving mobility, scalability, and security to avoid the limitations of underlying protocols. Therefore, this common Internet stack based on standardized protocols facilitates the development of IoMT solutions with seamless end-to-end communications via the Internet [2]. However, this common Internet stack inserts a relatively large overhead of IPv6, UDP, and CoAP headers per packet that is not feasible in some IoMT scenarios using LPWANs, e.g., LoRaWAN, Sigfox, with strong limitations in messages' length (e.g., LoRaWAN

packet with less than 128 bytes). To tackle that challenge, recently the IETF has proposed the SCHC [16] for enabling the adaption of IPv6 and UDP headers to constrain IoMT networks such as the aforementioned LPWANs.

2.2. Compression & fragmentation based on SCHC

SCHC provides header compression and optional packet fragmentation, designed to enable the transmission of IPv6 and UDP packets in IoT scenarios, especially in LPWAN-based architectures. Using header compression, a higher level of efficiency is gained, enabling the constrained network nodes' connectivity via the Internet. Additionally, to signalling payload size savings, there are improvements in the usage of radio spectrum and energy power. Since not all low-power technologies include a Minimum Transmission Unit (MTU) large enough to fit the IPv6 header 1280 B requirement [17], SCHC presents an optional fragmentation procedure tailored to the constrained links. Moreover, a new extension of SCHC is currently under standardization [18] by the IETF for compressing the CoAP header. Both standards based on SCHC provide efficient compression and fragmentation of the IPv6, UDP, and CoAP packets for allowing end-to-end communication of resource-limited IoT devices through the Internet. To achieve high efficiency in compression and fragmentation, SCHC leverages LPWAN features such as star-topology and regular well-known traffic flows between the data sources and destinations. These features allow SCHC to store data and define how to compress the fields of IPv6, UDP, and COAP communications in *rules*. Thus, every rule specifies a traffic flow and all rules are maintained in a unique static *context*. As a result, SCHC improves the radio bandwidth use and battery life-time, thus avoiding the synchronization signalling required in dynamic context protocols. Furthermore, SCHC is an upper-layer protocol, independent of the radio technology employed for sending and receiving packets.

One of the main SCHC features is its capacity to hide the constrained network architecture and details employed by the end device. Instead, all end devices are effortlessly integrated into IPv6 networks by identification with their own unique IPv6 address through standardized Internet protocols. SCHC is configurable and provides flexibility because of several configuration parameters. The adequate use-case scenarios for SCHC are those where the network administrators have a good notion of the type of messages being transmitted by end devices, such as the typical size and protocol stack employed, e.g., UDP and CoAP. In these cases, SCHC becomes highly efficient. Even in the worst-case scenario, when the original packet cannot be compressed, SCHC enables the transmission over LPWAN through a lightweight and configurable fragmentation and reassembly mechanism, which is not provided by the standard LPWANs' specification protocols, thus improving the network infrastructure capabilities.

2.3. Bootstrapping based on low-overhead CoAP-EAP (LO-CoAP-EAP)

Bootstrapping enables the initialization of an IoT device to obtain access data communication in a given network. Bootstrapping involves a set of security operations such as authentication, authorization, and key management, and it is of great importance for operators dealing with the massive numbers of IoT devices expected in large-scale deployments.

Typically, end devices transmitting over unconstrained networks perform bootstrapping by directly addressing any authentication server connected to an IP network. This exchange usually employs a standardized protocol such as Remote Authentication Dial-In User Service (RADIUS) [19] or Diameter [20] to transmit Extensible Authentication Protocol (EAP) [21] messages over regular IP networks. However, RADIUS and Diameter require an exchange of relatively large messages with several transmissions. This aspect exacerbates the problem of energy consumption and radio bandwidth usage because of header overhead for constrained radio technologies such as LoRaWAN. Furthermore, existing bootstrapping proposals are designed to the specific features of

Fig. 1. Proposed architecture.

the employed radio network technology, which does not allow the interoperability among different systems.

To address these issues, LO-CoAP-EAP [8] has been proposed as a network-independent bootstrapping solution for heterogeneous IoMT networks. The LO-CoAP-EAP design considers the constraints of LPWANs in computational and communication capabilities. To guarantee the desired interoperability, LO-CoAP-EAP is based on three Internet standards, namely, the AAA infrastructure, EAP, and CoAP. First, the AAA infrastructure enables scalability and roaming for network access authentication. Second, EAP allows different IoMT devices and organizations to use different authentication mechanisms (based on symmetric keys, certificates, etc.) depending on the requirements. Third, CoAP is an application protocol for IoT that enables Machine-to-Machine (M2M) communications. By building over these standardized protocols, LO-CoAP-EAP enables secure bootstrapping of distributed IoMT devices to maintain a decentralized Internet infrastructure. Recently, LO-CoAP-EAP has been validated in different IoMT networks, such as LoRaFabian [8] and a simulated scenario of Low-Rate Wireless Personal Area Networks (LR-WPANs) [22].

The research advances the development and evaluation of LO-CoAP-EAP bootstrapping in a real-world IoMT scenario, considering LPWANs as the communication infrastructure. To achieve these results, we have developed an MEC-based implementation of the SCHC mechanism for enabling the transport of LO-CoAP-EAP packets over constrained LPWAN links. We evaluated the performance of this implementation on a real LoRaWAN deployment, which presents notably limited bandwidth and packet lengths. This contribution permits the flexible authentication of IoMT units, regardless of the location of the device and the underlying LPWAN communication technology.

3. MEC-based architecture for interoperable and trustworthy IoMT

3.1. Standardization-based approach

The IoMT imposes an almost limitless and continuous working scenario in which every end device is able to obtain connectivity through one of the embedded RATs. Unfortunately, current IoMT solutions are mainly built on non-interoperable protocols for heterogeneous IoMT devices, which is usually based on proprietary protocols and private systems. This fact clearly hinders the development of interoperable and secure applications that satisfy strict requirements requested by international regulations such as (i) the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR¹) for data privacy and protection, (ii) the Directive on Security of

Network and Information Systems (NIS²) for internet operations, and (iii) the EU Regulation No 526/2013³ from the European Union Agency for Network and Information Security (ENISA).

The design of interoperability and security solutions for boosting the IoMT is currently a great challenge to overcome. In particular, end-to-end secure authentication and long-headers compression are key aspects to enable trustworthy and dynamic IoMT applications. However, typical well-known Internet protocols that may fill this gap, such as UDP, IPv6, Datagram Transport Layer Security (DTLS), or Transport Layer Security (TLS), among others, are too complex to be supported by constrained IoMT networks with limited bandwidth. In this line, the IETF is dedicating several Working Groups (WGs) to the secure integration of LPWAN technologies within the Internet [23]. Specifically, to address the security aspects of resource-limited devices, the Authentication and Authorization for Constrained Environments (ACE) WG is in charge of standardization tasks related to authentication and authorization. These technologies enable a secure access to resources stored in constrained devices through an addressable Unified Resource Identifier (URI). The IETF has identified a broad and diverse set of IoT use cases where authentication and authorization mechanisms are necessary [24]. These use cases leverage primarily on CoAP [15], which is similar to Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) in design, but with constrained devices and networks as application targets. CoAP provides an end-to-end request-response RESTful model that is centered around resources stored within the serving device, allowing the use of a unique URI to address such resources. Many technologies standardized by the IETF lean on CoAP, e.g., Concise Binary Object Representation (CBOR), CBOR Object Signing and Encryption (COSE), or Object Security for Constrained RESTful Environments (OSCORE) [23]. However, the security mechanisms that protect these communications depend on a secure authentication and key agreement stage where the constrained device gains access to the network and obtains a set of session keys employed during the rest of the operations.

As a consequence, due to the aforementioned advantages of the response-request model implemented via CoAP, the IETF is adopting this protocol in recent and on-going standardization efforts. End devices are expected to include encode–decode libraries within their firmware binary code. Hence, using technologies that leverage this serving layer saves space by avoiding the unnecessary code footprint overhead, and ensures compatibility with many technologies and scenarios. Among the different solutions that fit within this scope, this study focuses on the Low-Overhead CoAP-EAP protocol (LO-CoAP-EAP) [8]. As described above, this protocol is designed to provide authentication and key agreement mechanisms over low-bandwidth networks, such as LPWANs. Additionally, it leverages the CoAP application service layer to encode and address resources related to the bootstrapping process operations. The bootstrapping processes in LPWANs are restrictive when compared to other technologies such as IEEE 802.15.4 or Bluetooth Low Energy, which are also considered constrained solutions. For this reason, LPWANs usually rely on radio technology-specific protocols with lightweight intermediate layers that prevent high bandwidth overhead. These protocols are typically vendor-specific and do not take into consideration the integration with different LPWAN technologies. Following this strategy, IoMT systems that include end devices from different LPWAN families should incorporate an extra layer of complexity to enforce the individual access policies depending on the specific technology that is used by each type of end device. To solve this issue, our LO-CoAP-EAP-based solution relies on the AAA architecture, which makes the security and bootstrapping management easily extensible, and provides the flexibility required in heterogeneous IoMT deployments. In

² <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/network-and-information-security-nis-directive>.

³ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=OJ:JOL_2013_165_R_0041_01.

¹ <https://eugdpr.org/>.

addition, once a device is authenticated on the network infrastructure, the device's activities easily account for security or billing purposes.

To further increase the possibilities of the authentication and key agreement processes, LO-CoAP-EAP employs EAP, which is compatible with different authentication methods that can be adapted to the end device's capabilities and resources during the bootstrapping process. Besides, this strategy opens the door to future integration for these types of these systems within the 5G infrastructure, given the variety of supported authentication mechanisms.

In the light of the previous discussion, we propose the MEC-based trustworthy architecture presented in Fig. 1. The architecture is based on the integration of SCHC compression and secure LO-CoAP-EAP bootstrapping with an AAA infrastructure for IoMT networks. This architecture enables header compression and authenticates key management to facilitate secure end-to-end data protection at the application level with the independence of the underlying transmission network. The proposal aims to overcome the high heterogeneity of specific security mechanisms in the link layer provided by the different low-power wireless technologies. Currently, there are not any homogenization mechanisms to perform key management and end-to-end data protection among the low-power devices of different wireless networks. To address this issue, we combine SCHC and LO-CoAP-EAP mechanisms as an energy-efficient and lightweight solution in the application layer to enable the secure interoperability of different low-power wireless technologies through the Internet in a more decentralized, scalable, and trustworthy way. Specifically, the proposed architecture provides two key features: (i) secure bootstrapping for authentication and key establishment, and (ii) low protocol overhead to minimize the requirements of message size, memory, storage, and power consumption to fit the constrained IoMT wireless networks. To achieve the aforementioned features, the architecture includes the entities described in the following.

3.2. Architecture elements

3.2.1. IoMT device

The IoMT Device is a small form-factor and resource-limited hardware which sits on the edge of the IoMT network, and consists of the microcontroller, memory, input and output peripherals, communication module, etc. Each end device shall incorporate at least a low-power communication module to enable connectivity with the Internet through an LPWAN, e.g., LoRaWAN. These end devices are typically installed in hard-to-reach locations, placed in vehicles, or in adverse conditions such as extreme temperatures, submerged in toxic substances, installed in hazardous locations, sustaining extreme conditions, requiring rugged cases that prevent dust and water penetration, and are meant to work autonomously without human supervision for months or even years. For this purpose, these devices are commonly operated using small batteries and do not include user interfaces such as keypads or displays. Due to their small form-factor and lower power consumption, these end devices are relegated to very specific monitoring and actuation tasks with a simple operation logic that normally relies on data communications with a centralized cloud infrastructure. Additionally, their communication activities should be highly efficient as these tasks are highly power-consuming.

In the proposed architecture, an end device will be used to collect, format, and exchange sensor and actuation data with a cloud server or other target machine. The end device needs to authenticate before it connects to the target server or machine using a constrained network to achieve data exchange in a trustworthy way. As mentioned above, this operation should be highly efficient to avoid wasting energy.

3.2.2. LPWAN-based transmission technology

LPWAN-based Transmission Technology represents the set of services and protocols that enable access from end devices to the Internet. In this architecture, it is presented as a generic framework that can represent any of low-power wireless networking technologies, i.e., LPWANs.

Although each low-power network technology presents particular characteristics and limitations at the radio and link layers, all of them usually provide reduced transmission bit-rates and bandwidth, which severely limits the transmissions' lengths. Finally, each low-power network provides the back-end infrastructure in charge of exchanging packets with the nonconstrained side of Internet architecture side.

3.2.3. MEC node

This element hosts two crucial entities for the development of the proposed authentication and bootstrapping architecture: the Network Server (NS) and the SCHC module. The former is part of the back-end infrastructure of the low-power network. The MEC node represents the central hub for all the communications from and to low-power end devices. It aims to abstract the Physical (PHY) and Medium Access Control (MAC) layer details of the specific network technology to the components that must communicate with the end devices. The NS is in charge of collaborating with the end devices to maintain the overall network health, i.e., optimize the data-rate and overall energy consumption of the deployment site, as well as to orchestrate what radio configuration parameters end devices should employ to avoid packet loss or unnecessary retransmissions. This entity may be formed by multiple components in some low-power networks, e.g., such as LoRaWAN, which is based on the NS and Application Server (AS) that provide the complete network back-end infrastructure.

Regarding the SCHC compression and fragmentation operations, all the uplink transmissions received by the network server are forwarded to the SCHC reassembly and decompression module. The resulting IPv6 and UDP packets from this procedure are transmitted through the Internet, addressed at the IoMT controller. Likewise, the SCHC module is continuously listening to the IPv6 downlink LO-CoAP-EAP messages. Once received, the LO-CoAP-EAP message gets compressed and, optionally, split into SCHC fragments. These SCHC fragments are carried through the constrained link as application payload until reaching the IoMT device.

3.2.4. IoMT Controller

The IoMT Controller plays the role of the authenticator in AAA. End devices perform a bootstrapping process when they are deployed for the first time. This process includes an authentication and key agreement stage. Once the device successfully authenticates, session keys are shared with the device to securely perform the standard operation tasks.

In our case, the IoMT Controller includes the LO-CoAP-EAP protocol logic that parses the uplink messages transmitted by the end devices and forwards the contents to an authentication server that employs typical AAA protocols such as RADIUS or Diameter to carry the EAP payloads. Likewise, when the authentication server answers with the new downlink EAP messages, the IoMTController generates a new LO-CoAP-EAP packet and forwards it to the end device.

3.2.5. Authentication server

This entity provides an administrative end-point within the AAA architecture that abstracts the technology-specific details of the deployed end devices. Thus, the system administrator simply manages the identity and key materials, and relies on this element to employ the security mechanisms that fit each specific case. The authentication server employs EAP, which is a flexible solution that supports several methods, with various degrees of performance requirements for each end device. Conversely, more constrained devices may employ lightweight cryptographic primitives, such as AES with the EAP-PSK method. By contrast, other nonconstrained end devices may rely on more computationally demanding methods such as those based on public key infrastructure, or certificates.

First, the end device credentials and key information must be previously configured in the authentication server. Next, the end device will be installed on the deployment site and will perform the bootstrapping procedure. During the bootstrapping, the device will authenticate on the network and will obtain a set of session keys. Finally, the end device

Fig. 2. Diagram of end-to-end packets exchange in LO-CoAP-EAP.

finishes the bootstrapping procedure and begins the operational phase. The ultimate result of the bootstrapping process is attaining an encryption key that is securely stored within the end device. The encryption key will be employed for securing the following communications with the rest of the architecture components. The key is to be protected via anti-tampering techniques that prevent attackers from reading the key and obtaining physical access to the device to read the key.

3.2.6. Interactions

In the following, we present the end-to-end packets exchange for the authenticated key establishment between the IoMT controller and the IoMT device. Specifically, we have chosen LoRaWAN as the underlying transmission technology given their popularity and configuration options [9]. The designed workflow is shown in Fig. 2. SCHC allows the peer-to-peer fragmentation and compression for optimizing the packet length in the physical layer(PHY) link for a highly constrained network like LoRaWAN. The back-end of LoRaWAN infrastructure ensures that the packets are delivered to the SCHC module. This entity provides a communication abstraction for the concrete IoMT device by enabling an Application Interface (API) which is managed seamlessly by the compressor and decompressor of the SCHC mechanism. As aforementioned, SCHC reassembles and decompresses the original packet before transmitted it via the Internet.

Hence, by leveraging the adaptation layer provided by SCHC, the IoMT controller and the IoMT device are able to exchange the LO-CoAP-EAP headers through an end-to-end communication (IPv6, UDP, and CoAP). Next, the IoMT controller includes the EAP payload in an AAA mechanism (e.g., Diameter or RADIUS) to send the authentication data to an AAA server. According to the proposed MEC-based architecture, lower layers enable the packets delivery in the peer-to-peer authentication process. When the authentication procedure is initiated by the IoMT device, the first exchanged packet is a CoAP non-confirmable request. This is the only time that the IoMT controller plays the role of the CoAP server. For the rest of the LO-CoAP-EAP exchange, the IoMT device and controller switch roles; the IoMT device plays the role of the CoAP server instead of CoAP by answering the IoMT controller requests, which is in the form of uplink Acknowledgment Code (ACK) packets. The main reason is that each CoAP server is stateless and does not manage

retransmissions or timers. Therefore, the following messages after the first message are pairs of request-response started by the IoMT controller. Furthermore, the total number of packets relies on the selected EAP method.

Although the proposed solution is generic, for the implementation described in the next section, we have selected the Pre-Shared Key Extensible Authentication Protocol Method (EAP-PSK) because it requires relatively low computing capacities. This method requires six messages exchanged to complete the authentication procedure. Moreover, the packet pair always starts with a CoAP POST packet towards a target resource $/b$ initial, and $/b/x$ next. Additionally, it is used at a random digit (x) representing the Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) path of the CoAP resource for the bootstrapping procedure. The EAP packets are transported in the CoAP payload. An *AUTH* option of the CoAP header, which transports cryptodata, is included to enable the required key exchange. Additionally, the IoMT device responds by means of piggybacking the answer to the CoAP ACK frame. In some examples, cryptodata is transported as part of the Options in the CoAP header. Finally, once the last POST-ACK pair is exchanged, both end-parties (IoMT device and IoMT controller) locally compute a common Master Session Key (MSK). With this last exchange, the authenticated key establishment is finished at both ends.

4. Implementation and real-world deployment

As mentioned above, to validate the presented proposal, the architecture has been implemented and deployed with a real-world, low-power, and long-range network based on LoRaWAN technology.

4.1. IoMT end device

The Smart Everything (SME) Lion development board by Arrow⁴ has been employed as the testing end device, and SME is packed with the Atmel SAMD21 microcontroller based on the ARM Cortex M0+ architecture, the Microchip RN2483 LoRaWAN module, the Telit Jupiter SE868-A GPS module, the Microchip RN4871 BLE module, the Atmel AT24C256C 32Kx8 Bits EEPROM, and the Atmel ATECC508A crypto authentication chip. All the employed software required for this device to work is open source, which is released either as GNU's Not Unix (GNU) or Berkeley Software Distribution (BSD) licensed software. This software includes the compilation toolchain, the programming framework, peripheral drivers, and software libraries.

Regarding the RN2483 LoRaWAN module,⁵ it is a market-ready integrated module that implements a LoRaWAN Class A and C stack. The RN2483 is a certified LoRaWAN device; the LoRa Alliance guarantees the RN2483's compatibility with any LoRaWAN network that follows the official LoRaWAN Specification v1.0.2 [25]. This solution was preferred over other LoRaWAN chip models due to its popularity in both academia and industry. The communications with the module are done via ASCII commands over a Universal Asynchronous Receiver Transmitter (UART) interface, which accelerates development and debugging tasks.

4.2. MEC node

This element is a computer directly wired to the LoRaWAN gateway. The MEC Node's primary specifications are the following: Intel Core i5-7400 CPU at 3.00 GHz, 8GiB DIMM DDR4 Synchronous 2133 MHz, a 240 GiB SSD hard drive, which is connected to the net through an RTL8111/8168/8411 PCI Express Gigabit Ethernet. The operative system employed is an Ubuntu 20.04 server GNU and Linux distribution. As explained in the previous sections, the MEC node hosts two logical entities, which are described in the following sections.

⁴ <https://www.arrow.com/>.

⁵ <https://www.microchip.com/wwwproducts/en/RN2483>.

Table 1
IPv6 and SCHC packet size and compression ratios.

LO-CoAP-EAP	Direction	IPv6 packet size (B)	SCHC Packet without fragmentation (B)	CoAP Payload (B)	SCHC Compression Ratio (%)
Message 1	Uplink	85	16	8	18.8
Message 2	Downlink	98	32	29	32.6
Message 3	Uplink	131	66	60	50.3
Message 4	Downlink	130	65	59	50.0
Message 5	Uplink	110	48	43	43.6
Message 6	Downlink	100	28	4	28.0
Message 7	Uplink	85	19	0	22.3

4.2.1. LoRaWAN network server

The employed ChirpStack open-source LoRaWAN Network Server, which runs using a microservice technology, Docker. This server improves portability and guarantees that the deployment will not suffer from broken library compatibility or missing dependencies due to all the container images being stored in the Docker's official repositories. The official ChirpStack developers provide deployment configuration files⁶ via its own repository. This design choice facilitates the deployment and management solutions in different scenarios, thanks to the Docker's widespread availability.

4.2.2. SCHC module

The employed SCHC module runs as a separate process in the MEC node. To improve efficiency, the module has been developed using the C programming language and standard Unix networking libraries. The SCHC module continuously listens to all the Internet packets addressed to any of the IoT devices connected to the network via UDP sockets. Whenever a packet is received, it is redirected to the SCHC module's compression and fragmentation functions. The resulting downlink packet is forwarded to the constrained network server functions. The SCHC module interfaces with the network server through one of its exposed APIs. The preferred solution is to employ the message broker distributed with the ChirpStack.io microservice solution. This message broker uses a publication-subscription methodology that avoids unnecessary polling or other similar alternatives, such as RESTful APIs, through HyperText Transport Protocol Secure (HTTPS).

Table 1 presents the original LO-CoAP-EAP packet sizes and their compressed counterpart. SCHC's context defines the compression and decompression actions for each header field. These actions specify if the header field is sent over the network, or not sent over the network, which is truncated to a lesser number of bits, or mapped to some specific pre-established values. This context must be shared between both end-points before the device can operate, and is preprovided before deployment. There is no current standardized methodology defined within the scope of SCHC's RFC [16] to share or update the context over the radio link. Regarding compression, to achieve such ratios, all the IPv6 and UDP header values were defined as either "not-sent" or "compute". Please refer to [16] for further details of the context rules. Regarding the CoAP headers, a maximum compression ratio was intended. For reference, SCHC CoAP compression details are given in [18].

The CoAP Payload column in Table 1 shows the number of bytes included in the SCHC packet that belongs to the application payload. As such, there is no compression applied to those bytes, since it is outside of the CoAP headers' scope. LO-CoAP-EAP embeds some of the cryptographic material within the packet as CoAP Options, which are considered part of the CoAP header. This is because they do not belong to the CoAP message payload after the end-of-options marker — an octet with a value 0xFF that indicates the end of the CoAP headers. However, these options must be specified in the SCHC context as value-sent, due to their contents' unpredictability at the design stage. These CoAP Options carry crypto material, and as such, the contents are different during each authentication session.

SCHC packets larger than 40 Bytes were fragmented by the SCHC fragmentation mechanism, equally splitting the payload of the original into two parts. The fragment length corresponds to the *Tile size* in SCHC jargon, and is fully configurable by the network administrator. Please note that a shorter LoRaWAN message may improve the reception success rate, but also introduces extra overhead. The chosen *Tile size* value of 40 bytes was obtained as a result of previous experiments [7]. Additionally, each time a packet is fragmented, an extra byte is included in the transmission, and an extra four byte Message Integrity Check (MIC) field is only included in the last fragment only. Conversely, the extra octet indicates that the LoRaWAN message is an SCHC fragment as well as the Fragment Compressed Number (FCN) field [16]. In contrast, the extra four byte MIC is employed for reassembly verification when the last fragment is received. Since the resulting SCHC packets require 1–2 LoRaWAN messages, the presence of ACKs is not considered an improvement over the network bandwidth usage. Hence, the SCHC fragmentation reliability mode employed is No-ACK. In this mode, all the received fragments are concatenated in a reception buffer. When the last received fragment is signalled with an FCN containing all 1s, the message is checked against the trailing MIC. If the check is successful, the SCHC packet is considered as successfully reassembled. If the check fails, the whole buffer is silently dropped and a full retransmission is required. Regardless of using the No-ACK reliability mode at the SCHC adaptation layer, the application protocol executed above may achieve reliability by different means. First, LO-CoAP-EAP leverages on CoAP, which in turn is designed with constrained devices and networks in mind. Hence, taking into consideration lossy networks with relatively high error rates when compared to other wireless technologies. By contrast, LO-CoAP-EAP implements different reliability-ensuring mechanisms on the client side, like unique message identifiers or URI paths used locally to separate different requests. Conversely, LO-CoAP-EAP integrates duplicated packet handling on the server side. To facilitate this process, after handling a message, all the duplicated received copies, trigger the handled answer retransmission. Due to the aforementioned features, LO-CoAP-EAP is in charge of maintaining message delivery reliability by exploiting all the aforementioned mechanisms. Therefore, reliability is achieved when triggered retransmissions by a timer implemented on the IoT Controller side, as described in Section 4.4. Although SCHC's ACK reliability modes present a desirable option for nonreliable application layer protocols, this is not the case of LO-CoAP-EAP that has already been validated over lossy LR-WPANs [8].

4.3. Gateway

The LoRaWAN Gateway employed in this project is the Wirnet iStation,⁷ which is a rugged IP66 base station designed and developed by Kerlink. It includes the Semtech SX1301 high-performance radio module connected to a fully integrated internal LoRa antenna with a peak gain of 2.6 dBi, and an ARM Cortex A9 microprocessor, which connects to the back-haul network either via 4G connectivity module with 3G/2G fallback, or through Ethernet. In our case, we are utilizing the last option for directly connecting this module with the MEC node.

⁶ <https://github.com/brocaar/chirpstack-docker>.

⁷ <https://www.kerlink.com/product/wirnet-istation/>.

4.4. Testing scenarios

To validate the proposed architecture for secure authentication and key agreement, the chosen test bed is composed by a combination of one mobile scenario and three static (nomadic scenarios). The tests were performed by placing the end device on top of a car and circulating around the University of Murcia Campus in Espinardo, Spain. By contrast, during the mobile experiments, the car carrying the end device circulated at regular speeds on the campus at around 20 km/h. Conversely, during the nomadic tests, the car was stationed in different fixed locations on campus for the duration of the tests. Once each nomadic scenario was completed, the car moved to another location and started a new test.

In turn, the LoRaWAN gateway was installed on the roof of the Faculty of Computer Science building at the University of Murcia's Espinardo Campus, located at coordinates 38.023769, -1.1739583. The LoRaWAN gateway was connected to the MEC node through an Ethernet cable, and the LoRaWAN configuration employed a Class C setting. This means that the end device was continuously listening to the downlink packets during the entire duration of the authentication exchange. Additionally, nine different channels were employed during the tests. For the uplink communications, 8 different channels were employed, namely, 867.1, 867.3, 867.5, 867.7, 867.9, 868.1, 868.3, and 868.5 MHz. These channels were randomly chosen during each uplink communication. For the downlink communications, the channel 869.525 MHz was always employed as an RX2 channel for Class C communications. All the end device's uplink transmissions employed the unconfirmed LoRaWAN mode. This approach prevents the network from transmitting downlink ACK packets without application payload, since the tested exchange expects to receive the LO-CoAP-EAP messages. Each testing scenario was performed twice, with different LoRaWAN's data-rates values, namely, DR1 and DR4. For each of the scenarios, the same track or locations were employed. A summary of the different equipment configuration parameters employed in our experiments can be found in Table 2. Note that only the LoRa PHY Chirp Spread Spectrum (CSS) radio modulation was utilized. This is due to the LoRaWAN regional parameters which specify the radio parameters to use in the EU868 radio band for DR1 and DR4. Additionally, for the LoRa PHY coding rate parameter, a constant value of 4/5 was employed.

The IoMT controller was configured to perform up to four packet retransmissions with a timeout value of 7000 ms. This is, each time the IoMT controller sends a LO-CoAP-EAP message to the end device and does not receive a response within this time, a duplicate packet is obtained again until a response is gotten, or reaching four retries. As a consequence, when the end device receives a duplicated packet, it will trigger the same uplink response. Please note that, as described previously, the end device begins the authentication exchange by transmitting the first LO-CoAP-EAP message. However, the rest of exchanges, i.e., LO-CoAP-EAP messages 2-7, are initiated as CoAP confirmed posts from the IoMT controller. Hence, the IoMT controller is responsible for keeping track of the retransmission count and timeout triggers, while the end device simply keeps a copy of the last transmitted message in case of duplicated requests. Additionally, communications among the gateway, network server, IoMT controller, and the authentication server are not constrained and follow regular network retransmission policies for hosts connected to the Internet through reliable mediums such as Ethernet.

For each test, 10 authentication processes were launched by reinitiating the LO-CoAP-EAP authentication procedure from the end device each 80,000 ms, whether the previous authentication procedure was successful or not. This is not the regular behaviour of the operating devices, and is only meant to obtain more sampling data during the conducted experiments. However, under regular circumstances, once the device has successfully completed the authentication procedure, it will not repeat the exchange, as it keeps the attained session keys for a relatively long period of time. Additional details regarding each testing scenario are provided in the following.

Table 2

Summary of the equipment configuration.

	IoMT End Device	Gateway
Output Power	+14 dBm	+14 dBm
Antenna Gain	+2.2 dBi	+2.6 dBi
Radio Modulation	LoRa CSS	LoRa CSS
Bandwidth	125 kHz	125 kHz
Radio Band	ISM EU868	ISM EU868
RX Sensitivity DR4	-126.0 dBm	-129.0 dBm
RX Sensitivity DR1	-133.0 dBm	-136.5 dBm
Nominal Data-rate DR4	3125.00 bps	
Nominal Data-rate DR1	537.11 bps	

Fig. 3. Mobile scenario track points colored by elevation.

4.4.1. Mobile scenario

Fig. 3 shows the track points during the mobile experiments. Each track point is colored with the elevation, ranging from 129.5 to 178.7 m, in order to give a better sense of the scenario's characteristics. The Espinardo Campus, where the mobile tests were performed, contains large buildings of up to ten stories. The car circulated at an average speed of 19.86 km/h in traffic during regular campus activity at midday. For scale, the maximum distance between the gateway and the end device is also indicated, reaching 1.34 km (0.83 mi.).

4.4.2. Nomadic scenario

Fig. 4 presents the location points where the static tests were performed as well as their distance from the gateway. As can be seen, the experiments were conducted in eight different locations, labeled as A, B, C, D, E, F, G, and H. Additionally, to validate how the authentication exchange behaves in different scenario conditions, these nomadic locations are grouped based on two different qualitative variables. The locations are grouped by the degree of massive obstacles found in the line of sight between both end-points. Thus, experiment locations that present vegetation or buildings obstructing the line of sight are considered as

Fig. 4. Nomadic scenario location points.

unfavorable, while locations that lack such obstacles are considered as favorable. Notably, the nomadic locations are also grouped by the elevation profile found in the straight line from end to end. In this case, the profiles considered are concave and convex. In particular, when the elevation profile found in the direct route from the gateway to the device presents a concave form, the location is considered as favorable. Contrarily, when the elevation profile presents a convex shape, the location is considered as unfavorable. In this manner, the nomadic locations showcased in Fig. 4 are categorized as follows. Regarding the level of obstacles, points A, B, C, and F do not present massive structures or vegetation obstructing the line of sight. Therefore, they are considered as favorable. Conversely, points D, E, G, and H introduce severe obstacles and are considered as unfavorable in this aspect. In the same way, considering the elevation profile between the gateway and the end device, points A, D, E, and F draw a concave elevation profile. Thus, they are considered as favorable. Yet, points B, C, G, and H present a convex profile, and are considered as unfavorable. Notably, each possible combination of both qualitative variable values incorporates two different locations with the aim of further validating how the terrain conditions or the presence of obstacles affect the authentication protocol exchange. For this purpose, during these tests the same end device setup as in the mobile scenario was employed, and the car carrying the end device was always parked at road level.

5. Evaluation and results

To explore the reliability of the system, we first analyze the Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR) among the different components of the architecture. We differentiate the constrained radio link, i.e., LoRaWAN, and the nonconstrained radio link, i.e., gateway, network server, IoMT controller, and the authentication server. As expected, no packet losses or timeouts were detected in the nonconstrained links during the realization of the experiments. For this reason, we consider only the delivery ratio of the

Table 3
Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR) per scenario.

Scenario	PDR Uplink (%)	PDR Downlink (%)
Mobile DR1	97.4	79.4
Mobile DR4	87.5	72.7
Nomadic A DR1	100	77.6
Nomadic A DR4	100	85.7
Nomadic B DR1	100	81.8
Nomadic B DR4	100	98.2
Nomadic C DR1	97.3	79.5
Nomadic C DR4	94.6	90.3
Nomadic D DR1	98.7	83.1
Nomadic D DR4	94.0	93.9
Nomadic E DR1	97.4	82.3
Nomadic E DR4	97.1	90.9
Nomadic F DR1	95.2	81.9
Nomadic F DR4	84.6	89.4
Nomadic G DR1	88.4	78.9
Nomadic G DR4	18.5	92.3
Nomadic H DR1	36.8	26.3
Nomadic H DR4	0	0

constrained link as a relevant factor for these results, which are shown in Table 3. Considering the previous, in this case the PDR gives the indication of how adverse the radio conditions performed during the tests. Depending on the number of obstacles, road traffic, and the terrain characterization, radio communications may be affected. Normally, low-bandwidth networks such as LoRaWAN are capable of tolerating relatively low PDR values such as 60% or more; however, at PDR values below 40%, the exchange of messages during the authentication procedure is severely hindered. Additionally, lower Data-Rate (DR) values are typically more reliable than the higher ones. In general, this is the behaviour observed in the attained results, except in two downlink cases, where the attained difference is not highly notable. The results indicate that the radio conditions at the nomadic scenarios G and H are the worst of the set. As aforementioned in Section 4.4.2, nomadic scenarios G and H present unfavorable conditions with regard to the presence of massive obstacles. A convex elevation profile among the gateway and the car positions provoked severe coverage problems. Consequently, these points presented important problems in accomplishing a full authentication as explained in the following.

Regarding the entire authentication process, Table 4 presents the rate of authentication success in each scenario, considering that the overall number of authentication attempts was 10 per scenario. Focusing on the mobile scenario, now it was clearly seen the robustness provided by the DR1 configuration in comparison with the DR4 can clearly be seen. Regarding the static experiments (nomadic), an almost perfect success rate was attained except for the problematic G and H locations. Notably, although in Table 3 imperfect PDRs below 100% were obtained, and in Table 4 we observe very high authentication success rates. This result is explained by the packet retransmission procedure of LoRaWAN technology, which was previously explained. Overall, it can be seen that the performance of the proposal is notably successful when the radio coverage is not dramatically deficient.

The statistical data concerning the time that it takes the authentication procedure to finish a complete exchange is presented in Fig. 5. The authentication time includes the full exchange of the seven LO-CoAP-EAP messages, including occasional retransmissions and time delays. Note that the nomadic scenario H has been excluded in this figure because no authentication exchange was completed successfully in a timely fashion, i.e., within the 80 s time-limit imposed as a network management policy. Likewise, in the nomadic scenario G, no successful authentication exchange was achieved with DR4. Hence, Fig. 5 shows an empty space for this configuration. This is a consequence of the adverse radio conditions encountered at those locations, as explained above. However, for the rest of the scenarios, the authentication procedure was successfully completed in a timely fashion. These exchanges took an average of 22–39 s, for DR4 and DR1 scenarios, respectively. These results expose

Table 4
Authentication success rate per scenario.

Scenario	Auth. Attempts	Auth. Success (%)
Mobile DR1	10	80
Mobile DR4	10	50
Nomadic A DR1	10	90
Nomadic A DR4	10	100
Nomadic B DR1	10	100
Nomadic B DR4	10	100
Nomadic C DR1	10	90
Nomadic C DR4	10	100
Nomadic D DR1	10	100
Nomadic D DR4	10	90
Nomadic E DR1	10	100
Nomadic E DR4	10	100
Nomadic F DR1	10	100
Nomadic F DR4	10	100
Nomadic G DR1	10	70
Nomadic G DR4	10	0
Nomadic H DR1	10	0
Nomadic H DR4	10	0

the problems endured by LoRa caused by the presence of massive obstacles, such as dense vegetation or concrete and steel buildings, especially when found in the line of sight among the end points. In turn, the characterization of the terrain elevation profile has fewer impacts; although the combination of a convex profile together with the presence of obstacles leads to notably poor coverage levels. Furthermore, the results indicate that the DR has an impact on the overall time that it takes for the exchange to fully complete. This result is due to the longer time-on-air period that it takes to transmit these messages using DR1 in comparison with that of DR4. Nevertheless, as aforementioned, lower DR values are required to cover large coverage areas, as opposed to higher DR values that permit shorter time-on-air values and a lower packet collision probability.

6. Conclusion

The current IoMT landscape is composed of devices with vastly heterogeneous computing and networking capabilities. For this reason, realizing solutions enabling Internet connectivity of the constrained devices via multi-RAT deployments is a current challenge for both academia

and industry. Common security and authentication solutions are not adequate for the severe constraints that are typical in battery-powered devices. As such, supporting secure and lightweight authentication procedures is attracting the attention of different standardization bodies such as IETF. Thus, this study presents a novel proposal to perform an efficient authentication and key agreement procedure in the low-bandwidth networks such as LPWANs. This solution does not rely on vendor-specific technologies or closed protocols, instead the presented proposal leverages open specifications and open protocol standardization efforts by IETF. The main pillars of our solutions include LPWAN technologies as the transmission solution for the communications of battery-powered constrained devices, the SCHC scheme for the IPv6, UDP and CoAP header compression and fragmentation, the LO-CoAP-EAP mechanism as a low-overhead lightweight secure authentication, and the key agreement procedure, compatible with the AAA framework. The proposal has been implemented employing a real LoRaWAN deployment, including constrained embedded devices. To validate the model's feasibility, a set of mobile and static test scenarios were employed to evaluate the performance of the proposal. The results demonstrate that IoMT devices can leverage the SCHC and LO-CoAP-EAP technologies to obtain IPv6 connectivity, as well as to perform secure bootstrapping procedures in a timely fashion. The authentication success ratio has shown a very good performance of nearly 100% in the static scenarios with good coverage conditions and more than 80% in the dynamic scenarios.

In future work, we plan to include in the proposed architecture a novel IETF standard, so-called OSCORE to leverage the key established in the authentication process to maintain a secure end-to-end data protection at the application level with low-power network independence. Additionally, new research will be conducted in the compression of the EAP header fields via the SCHC generic framework technique, as a method to complement the current standardization efforts for IPv6, UDP and CoAP header compression. Finally, we also plan to evaluate the proposed scheme and further developments in other LPWAN-based solutions.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Fig. 5. Authentication time per scenario.

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